

1 **BCL family modulation during transformation and senescence.**

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6 The pro- and anti- apoptotic cell death regulators encoded by the BCL gene family control decisions
7 affecting survival of the cell and function at the level of the mitochondria and induction of apoptotic cell
8 death through a membrane permeabilization event known as mitochondrial outer membrane
9 permeabilization (MOMP) which triggers release of apoptotic like cytochrome C, resulting in activation of
10 initiator and executioner caspases. We studied two separate models of senescence in human cells in vitro
11 to describe BCL family activation and repression as a component of the senescence program. We also
12 measured total transcription in human cells expressing a wild-type Ras oncogene, KRas, or an oncogenic
13 variant, KRas G12V, to understand how the BCL gene family influenced senescence induction during
14 oncogene-induced senescence or senescence induction by a mutant oncogene. Senescence was
15 characterized by induction of *BAD*, a pro-apoptotic effector, consistent with the defining feature of
16 senescence, a halt in cell cycle proliferation driven by activation of genes encoded by the cyclin dependent
17 kinase inhibitor (CDKN) family. *BAD* induction was conserved and quantitatively similarly both when
18 studying fibroblasts isolated from young and aged humans, and when studying senescence independent
19 of aging, in a replicative senescence model. During transformation of human cells, the major BCL gene
20 family member activated was *BCL2L11*, a pro-apoptotic effector also known as BIM. BIM was activated
21 during oncogene-induced senescence, analogous to activation of *BAD* in natural senescence, while in
22 cells undergoing transformation associated with senescence bypass resulting from expression of a mutant
23 oncogene, BIM was instead repressed. Similarly, the executioner caspase *CASP7* was repressed by KRas
24 G12V but activated by wild-type KRas. Human cells integrate cell cycle decisions by control of CDK and
25 CDKN gene expression with cell death decisions by control of the BCL gene family to produce a binary
26 outcome resulting in a cellular state featuring either net survival together with support of proliferative
27 capacity (senescence bypass, or transformation) or a survival outcome that favors a spectrum of cell
28 death decisions that each are net death outcomes which occurs together with induction of a proliferative
block (senescence).